

ENTREPRENEURSHIP EDUCATION AND YOUTHS EMPOWERMENT IN AHOADA EAST LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA RIVERS STATE

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ABSTRACT: This study investigated on Entrepreneurship Education and Youths Empowerment in Ahoada East Local Government Area of Rivers State. The study was guided by three hypotheses and objectives. The study examined the relationship between entrepreneurship education and youths' empowerment. The anchored on the theory of human capital. The study adopted correlational and cross-sectional research design. The population of the study was youths across the Local Government Area with a purposive sample size of 265 youths was used, structured questionnaire with 4 Likert scale was used as main source of data collection. PPMCC was used to test the hypotheses at .05 alpha level with the help of SPSS model. The findings of this study revealed that there was a low positive significant relationship between cognitive domain and in Ahoada East Local Government Rivers State. The findings of this study showed that there was a low positive significant relationship between affective, psychomotor and youths' empowerment in Ahoada East Local Government Rivers State. The study concluded that entrepreneurship education is inevitable to advance youths empowerment for economic growth. Based on this, the study further recommended that parents, entrepreneurs, government and society should encourage the spirit of capitalism to empower youths to be job creators for nation building and economic growth of the economy.

Keywords: Cognitive Domain, Affective Domain, Psychomotor Domain, Youths' Empowerment, Ahoada East LGA, Rivers State, Nigeria.

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INTRODUCTION

The study of entrepreneurship has geometrically increased as a driving force for creative, innovation, resources optimization, self-reliance, employment opportunity, economic growth both developed and developing economy. In recent decades, rising unemployment, especially among youths, and the limited capacity of the public sector to absorb labour have compelled governments at various to organise and promote entrepreneurship development institutions as a sustainable pathway to youths' empowerment (Acs et al., 2021; GEM, 2023). In developing countries such as Nigeria, entrepreneurship is particularly vital because it supports self-

employment, stimulates small business formation, and enhances household income and living conditions.

Entrepreneurship education is a formal forum of educating, acquainting trainees with the requisite fundamental concepts, knowledge, attitudes and practical skills necessary for venture creation and sustainability of the economy. Entrepreneurship education is conceptualized into three interrelated domains: cognitive, affective, and psychomotor domains (Fayolle & Gailly, 2023; Ndofirepi, 2022). The cognitive domain relates to educating the trainees basic principles, theories, knowledge, awareness, enabling youths to understand business processes and recognise business ideas, opportunities, feasibility analysis and business plan to kick start venture creation. The affective domain focuses on creativity attitude, financial risk attitude, innovation mindset, uncertainty absorption on the dynamic and competitive business environment among others. The psychomotor domain addresses on skills, ability, capacity and competence of the trainees or the youths' to apply the various skills acquired through the program to practical sing them by being self-efficacy, self-reliance and venture creation for economic growth (Neck & Corbett, 2021). This implies that the essence of entrepreneurship education is aimed at skills acquisition for job creation as oppose job seekers in the economy.

Scholars commonly assess venture creation as a measure for youths' empowerment, employment generation and human capital development, earning living, self-reliance, job creators against job seekers, economic empowerment, particularly in growing and developing economy against unemployment and poverty (Acs et al., 2022). Employment generation includes both self-employment and job creation for others, while economic empowerment reflects income growth and improvements in living conditions. These outcomes are essential for achieving inclusive growth and reducing socio-economic vulnerabilities at the community level (UNDP, 2023).

In Nigeria, entrepreneurship education has been widely adopted across tertiary institutions, vocational centres and government-sponsored programmes as a strategy for addressing unemployment and fostering self-reliance. Despite these initiatives, unemployment rates remain high, and many trained individuals struggle to convert acquired entrepreneurial competencies into sustainable ventures (National Bureau of Statistics, 2023; Ogunleye & Awodun, 2022).

It is against this backdrop that this study investigates the relationship between entrepreneurship education and youth empowerment in Ahoada East local Government Area of Rivers State.

Statement of the Problem

The rate of unemployment, youths restiveness, social vices, idle resources raw materials and labour crises, low gross domestic products (GDP), low national income, dependent on politics as mean of earning, increase on National Youths Service Corps (NYSC) only depends on white-collar job that is not enough with numbers of the graduates in Nigeria, specifically in Ahoada East local Government Area of Rivers State. The researchers have observed over the years that entrepreneurship education have not been able to impact on youths' requisite knowledge, attitudes and skills that can enable self-employment and sustainability of the economy. In response to these concerns, effective entrepreneurship education has increasingly been emphasised that it has the potential to venture and create viable youths cognitive, affective, and psychomotor competencies. Components such as start-up knowledge, opportunity awareness,

risk attitude, innovation mindset, business skills and practical ability are expected to enhance individuals' capacity to identify opportunities and establish viable ventures (Fayolle & Gailly, 2023; Ndofirepi, 2022). However, empirical evidence from Nigeria remains inconclusive, as many studies focus primarily on entrepreneurial intention rather than actual venture creation outcomes. Therefore, this study investigated the effect of entrepreneurship education on venture creation in Ahoada East Local Government Area, Rivers State to determine entrepreneurial education potential in developing youth empowerment.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The aim and the study specifically objectives to:

- Investigate the relationship between the cognitive domain and Youths empowerment in Ahoada East Local Government Area Rivers State.
- Assess the relationship between the affective domain and Youths empowerment in Ahoada East Local Government Area Rivers State.
- Examine the relationship between the psychomotor domain and Youths empowerment in Ahoada East Local Government Area Rivers State.

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated to guide the study:

- There is no significant relationship between the cognitive domain and Youths empowerment Ahoada East Local Government Area Rivers State.
- There is no significant relationship between the affective domain and Youths empowerment Ahoada East Local Government Area Rivers State.
- There is no significant relationship between the psychomotor domain and Youths empowerment Ahoada East Local Government Area Rivers State.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Human Capital Theory

Human Capital Theory has been able to explain how investment in education, training, health, and skills enhances individuals' productivity and contributes to economic and social development. The theory is rooted in classical economics but was systematically developed in the mid-twentieth century, particularly through the works of Schultz in 1961 and Becker in 1964. The theory assumes that individuals' knowledge and competencies function as a form of capital that yields returns in the form of higher productivity, earnings, and societal growth (Schultz, 1961; Becker, 1964).

According to Human Capital Theory, education is not merely a social service but an economic investment that improves workers' skills, adaptability, and innovative capacity. Formal schooling, on-the-job training, and lifelong learning are viewed as mechanisms for accumulating human capital, which in turn enhances labor efficiency and organizational performance. Becker (1964) argued that individuals and societies incur costs in acquiring

education and training but expect future benefits such as increased income, employment opportunities, and economic competitiveness.

The theory also emphasized the role of governments and institutions in financing and supporting education and training systems. To Psacharopoulos and Patrinos (2018), public investment in education is justified because human capital generates positive externalities, including technological advancement, improved health outcomes, reduced poverty and social stability. In developing countries, Human Capital Theory has been widely applied to explain the link between educational expansion and national development, highlighting education as a key driver of productivity and economic growth.

Despite its influence, Human Capital Theory has been criticized for overemphasizing economic returns and underplaying social, cultural, and structural factors that affect educational outcomes and labor market rewards. Critics have continually argued that inequalities in access to education and employment can limit the realization of human capital benefits (Marginson, 2019). Nonetheless, the theory remains a foundational framework for understanding the economic value of education and skills development in contemporary societies.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Source: Adopted from Fayolle and Gailly (2023), Ndofirepi (2022) and Acs et al. (2021).

Entrepreneurship Education

Entrepreneurship education refers to the organized process through which individuals or trainees acquire the knowledge, attitudes, and practical abilities required to identify business opportunities, create ventures, and manage them successfully. It goes beyond teaching people how to start businesses; it focuses on shaping how individuals think, behave, and act in uncertain and dynamic environments. In recent years, entrepreneurship education has gained strong attention globally as governments and institutions seek sustainable solutions to unemployment, poverty, and weak economic growth, especially in developing economies such as Nigeria (Fayolle & Gailly, 2023; Ndofirepi, 2022). This makes it particularly relevant in contexts where

formal employment opportunities are limited, and self-employment becomes a necessary pathway for livelihood (Neck & Corbett, 2021). Entrepreneurship education is structured using the three domains of learning (cognitive, affective and psychomotor).

Cognitive Domain

The cognitive domain relates to the knowledge and intellectual understanding of entrepreneurship. It includes start-up knowledge, business planning, market analysis, financial literacy, and opportunity awareness. Cognitive learning helps aspiring entrepreneurs make informed decisions and reduces uncertainty associated with venture creation (Fayolle & Gailly, 2023). The cognitive domain represents the knowledge-based aspect of entrepreneurship education and focuses on how individuals understand, process, and apply entrepreneurial information. It is concerned with what people know about entrepreneurship and how that knowledge shapes their ability to recognise opportunities, make informed decisions, and plan viable ventures. Without adequate cognitive development, individuals may possess motivation or practical skills but still struggle to organise ideas, analyse markets, or structure sustainable businesses (Fayolle & Gailly, 2023).

Start-up knowledge refers to the understanding individuals possess about the processes, requirements, and activities involved in establishing a new business. It includes knowledge of business registration, basic accounting, pricing, marketing, financing, and operational planning. Start-up knowledge enables aspiring entrepreneurs to move from an idea stage to actual business formation in a structured and informed manner. In entrepreneurship education, this form of knowledge is considered essential because it reduces uncertainty and improves the quality of entrepreneurial decisions (Neck & Greene, 2021). When individuals are equipped with this knowledge, entrepreneurship education contributes to employment generation and income growth at the grassroots level (Acs et al., 2022). Opportunity awareness refers to the ability to recognise favourable market gaps, evaluate, and exploit business opportunities by venture creation fill the gap for profit making a sustainability of the economy. Opportunity awareness is a central element of the cognitive domain because it shapes how individuals perceive and respond to their environment (Shane, 2021). By improving opportunity awareness, entrepreneurship education supports the creation of ventures that can expand, employ others, and improve living conditions over time (Acs et al., 2021).

Affective Domain

The affective domain focuses on attitudes, re-engineering mindset to values; financial risk taking, proactiveness, innovativeness, resources mobilization, creativity, opportunities search and identification of market gap and emotional orientation toward entrepreneurship (Ndofirepi, 2022). The affective domain represents the attitude-based component of entrepreneurship education and focuses on how individuals feel, think, and emotionally respond to entrepreneurial activities. It deals with values, beliefs, motivation, and mindset that influence a person's willingness to engage in entrepreneurship and persist despite challenges. While knowledge and skills are important, entrepreneurship often involves uncertainty, risk, and repeated failure, making attitudes and emotions a critical part of venture creation. The affective domain therefore explains why some individuals act entrepreneurially while others with similar knowledge do not (Ndofirepi, 2022).

In entrepreneurship education, the affective domain is concerned with shaping positive perceptions toward entrepreneurship as a career path. It seeks to build confidence, resilience, creativity, and openness to learning. Individuals who develop strong affective competencies are more likely to view challenges as opportunities for growth rather than as barriers. This mindset supports persistence and adaptability, which are essential qualities for sustaining entrepreneurial ventures in dynamic business environments (Fayolle & Gailly, 2023).

The affective domain also influences how individuals perceive and manage risk. Entrepreneurship requires decision-making under uncertainty, where outcomes are not guaranteed. Attitudes toward risk, failure, and innovation determine whether individuals are willing to commit resources and effort to new ventures. Entrepreneurship education plays a key role in reshaping fear of failure into calculated risk-taking, helping individuals understand that failure can be a learning process rather than a permanent setback (Neck & Corbett, 2021).

In developing economies such as Nigeria, the affective domain is especially important due to economic instability, limited access to finance, and weak institutional support. These conditions often discourage entrepreneurial action, even among individuals who possess business knowledge, and by strengthening positive attitudes and innovative thinking, entrepreneurship education helps individuals remain motivated and proactive despite environmental constraints. To Acs et al. (2021), emotional readiness supports venture creation and contributes to employment generation and economic empowerment at the local level.

The affective domain also supports creativity and innovation. Entrepreneurs are expected to think differently, identify new ways of delivering value, and adapt to changing market needs. An innovative mindset allows individuals to move beyond imitation and engage in value creation that can sustain business growth. Entrepreneurship education nurtures this mindset by encouraging experimentation, curiosity, and openness to new ideas (Fayolle & Gailly, 2023).

Affective domain of entrepreneurship education in this context captured two key indicators: risk attitude and innovation mindset. Risk attitude refers to an individual's perception of and response to uncertainty and potential loss in entrepreneurial activities. It reflects the extent to which a person is willing to take calculated risks when pursuing business opportunities. Entrepreneurship inherently involves uncertainty, as outcomes cannot be fully predicted. Risk attitude therefore plays a significant role in determining whether individuals decide to start ventures, invest resources, or expand business operations (Ndofirepi, 2022).

Entrepreneurship education influences risk attitude by helping individuals understand and manage risk rather than avoid it entirely. Through learning experiences, individuals are exposed to concepts such as risk assessment, contingency planning, and informed decision-making. This exposure reduces fear of uncertainty and encourages a balanced approach to risk-taking, where decisions are based on analysis rather than impulse or fear (Neck & Greene, 2021).

To Fayolle and Gailly (2023), risk attitude reflects how entrepreneurship education shapes individuals' willingness to engage in venture creation despite uncertainty. Innovation mindset refers to an individual's orientation toward creativity, experimentation, and the generation of new ideas in entrepreneurial activities. It reflects the willingness to think differently, challenge existing practices, and develop novel solutions to problems. An innovative mindset is essential for entrepreneurs seeking to create value and remain competitive in changing markets.

Entrepreneurship education promotes innovation mindset by encouraging creativity, problem-solving, and continuous learning. Individuals are trained to observe their environment, identify unmet needs, and design solutions that improve products, services, or processes. This

mindset shifts entrepreneurship from mere survival activity to value-driven venture creation, which is more likely to support long-term growth (Ndofirepi, 2022). Neck and Corbett (2021) noted that innovation mindset captures the extent to which entrepreneurship education nurtures creativity and openness to new ideas among individuals in Ahoada Local Government Area Rivers State. It reflects the emotional and cognitive readiness to pursue innovative ventures that contribute to employment and improved living conditions.

Therefore, within the context of this study, the affective domain is important because venture creation outcomes do not only depend on what individuals know or can do, but also on how they think and feel about entrepreneurship. Employment generation and economic empowerment require persistence, confidence, and willingness to innovate over time. Entrepreneurs must be prepared to face uncertainty, competition, and policy-related challenges. The affective domain therefore provides the emotional and psychological foundation needed to sustain entrepreneurial efforts in Ahoada East Local Government Area.

Psychomotor Domain

Psychomotor domain of entrepreneurship education is captured through two key indicators: business skills and practical ability. Through this domain acquaint youths or trainees to acquire requisite skills. Business skills refer to the practical abilities and competencies required for venture creation and sustainable management to attain the goal and objectives effectively and efficiently. Skills acquired through entrepreneurial exposure in workshops, seminars, internships, apprenticeships, and practical training exercises. This practical exposure strengthens their readiness for venture creation (Ndofirepi, 2022). Trainees are often required to perform multiple tasks, including production, marketing, customer service, and financial management.

Entrepreneurship education that emphasises practical skills therefore plays a critical role in supporting self-employment and job creation at the grassroots level (Acs et al., 2021). These skills include basic financial management, record keeping, marketing, customer relations, inventory control, and decision-making. Business skills enable entrepreneurs to organise resources, monitor performance, and maintain day-to-day operations in a structured manner. In entrepreneurship education, the development of business skills is essential for translating ideas into sustainable ventures (Fayolle & Gailly, 2023). Business skills training, individuals learn how to price products, manage cash flow, communicate with customers, and plan business activities (Ndofirepi, 2022, Neck & Corbett, 2021). Nigerian context, many small businesses fail due lack of these skills (Acs et al., 2021). Practical ability also supports resilience and adaptability (Fayolle & Gailly, 2023).

Youths Empowerment

Youths Empowerment is a process creating, providing human capital requisite skills, experience, competences to be self-reliance, self-employment among others. Self-employment refers to the ability of individuals to create work for themselves through entrepreneurship education (Audretsch et al., 2022). Entrepreneurship education supports self-employment by equipping individuals with the knowledge, attitudes, and skills needed to operate independent ventures. Self-employment reflects the capacity of entrepreneurship education to enable individuals in Ahoada East Local Government Area to sustain themselves economically through venture creation. Employment generation therefore reflects the practical contribution of entrepreneurship

education on economic stability and social well-being (Acs et al., 2021). Venture creation supports employment generation by enabling individuals to convert business ideas into income-yielding activities. When individuals psychomotor establish ventures, they create work for themselves and, in many cases, gradually expand operations to engage additional labour.

In the Nigerian context, employment generation through venture creation plays a critical role in addressing youth unemployment. Venture creation serves as a grassroots solution to unemployment and a driver of local economic participation (National Bureau of Statistics, 2023). Jobs created refer to the number of employment opportunities generated by an entrepreneurial venture beyond the business owner. This includes paid workers, apprentices, or individuals engaged in regular business activities. Job creation reflects the growth and expansion of entrepreneurial ventures and their capacity to absorb labour within the community. Ventures that create jobs contribute directly to reducing unemployment and strengthening household incomes (Acs et al., 2022). Job creation, venture creations distribute economic benefits across a wider segment of the population. Workers gain income, skills, and work experience that improve their employability and economic security. Jobs created capture the extent to which entrepreneurship education in Ahoada East Local Government Area provide employment opportunities for others. It reflects the contribution of venture creation to labour absorption and community-level economic participation.

Relationship between Cognitive Domain and Youths empowerment

The cognitive domain of entrepreneurship education plays a significant role in shaping employment generation through venture creation. The cognitive domain focuses on the knowledge and understanding individuals possess about business start-up processes, market dynamics, and opportunity recognition. This knowledge enables entrepreneurs to plan, organise, and manage ventures in a way that supports business sustainability and economic growth (Fayolle & Gailly, 2023). Cognitive competence contributes directly to job creation by supporting structured and growth-oriented venture development (Neck & Corbett, 2021). Opportunity awareness also strengthens employment generation by enabling entrepreneurs to identify unmet needs and market gaps that can support scalable business ideas. When entrepreneurs can recognise viable opportunities, they are more likely to establish ventures with growth mindset and sustainability (Acs et al., 2021). Cognitive domain provides employment opportunities by shaping trainees understanding and management venture creation in return to earn a living. It enhances the capacity of ventures to create jobs and contributes to employment growth within the local economy.

Relationship between Affective Domain and Youths empowerment

The affective domain influences employment generation by shaping entrepreneurs' attitudes toward risk, persistence, and innovation. Employment requires more than knowledge; it requires willingness to take risks, confidence to expand operations, and motivation to manage people. These attributes are developed through the affective component of entrepreneurship education (Ndofirepi, 2022). Risk attitude plays a critical role in employment generation. Entrepreneurs who are willing to take calculated risks are more likely to invest in business expansion, introduce new products, and employ additional workers (Neck & Greene, 2021). Innovation mindset also contributes to employment generation by driving business growth. Entrepreneurs who think

creatively are more likely to improve products, explore new markets, and differentiate their ventures. Overall, the affective domain supports employment generation by shaping growth-oriented attitudes. Through positive risk attitude and innovation mindset, entrepreneurship education encourages entrepreneurs to move beyond self-employment toward job-creating ventures.

Relationship between Psychomotor Domain and Youths empowerment

The psychomotor domain influences employment generation by determining entrepreneurs' ability to execute business activities effectively. According to Neck and Corbett (2021), the practical skills developed through entrepreneurship education are therefore essential for job creation. Business skills enable entrepreneurs to organise operations, manage workers, and maintain productivity. Entrepreneurs who possess strong managerial and operational skills are better positioned to expand ventures and employ others. These skills support the development of stable enterprises that can sustain employment over time (Fayolle & Gailly, 2023). Practical ability further strengthens employment generation by enabling entrepreneurs to respond to daily operational challenges. Entrepreneurs who can apply skills effectively are more likely to maintain business continuity and growth. This growth creates demand for additional labour, supporting employment generation within the community (Ndofirepi, 2022).

Relationship between Psychomotor Domain and Economic Empowerment

The psychomotor domain is directly linked to economic empowerment because practical competence influences income generation and business sustainability. Entrepreneurs who can apply skills effectively are more likely to operate profitable ventures that provide stable income and improve living conditions (Fayolle & Gailly, 2023). Business skills support economic empowerment by improving efficiency and reducing operational losses. Entrepreneurs who manage finances, marketing, and customer relations effectively are better positioned to increase income. This income growth supports household welfare and long-term financial security (Acs et al., 2021). Thus, the psychomotor domain strengthens economic empowerment by enabling effective business execution that supports income growth and improved living standards.

EMPIRICAL REVIEW

Okafor (2020) examined the effect of entrepreneurship education on self-employment among graduates of tertiary institutions in Anambra State. The population of the study consisted of 520 graduates of selected tertiary institutions. A sample of 210 respondents was selected using stratified sampling techniques and regression analysis. The findings revealed that entrepreneurship education had a significant positive effect on self-employment. The study recommended that tertiary institutions should strengthen entrepreneurship curricula with more practical content to improve graduate self-employment. The study concluded that entrepreneurship education plays a vital role in reducing graduate unemployment through self-employment creation.

Eze and Nwankwo (2021a,b) studied the relationship between entrepreneurship education and job creation among small business owners in Enugu State. The population consisted of 460 registered small business owners. A sample of 180 respondents was selected using purposive

sampling technique and regression analysis. The findings indicated that start-up knowledge and business skills significantly influenced job creation. The study recommended that entrepreneurship training programmes should focus more on practical business skills. The study concluded that

Uche and Bassey (2023) examined the influence of entrepreneurship education on employment generation among small and medium enterprises in Akwa Ibom State. The population consisted of 690 SME operators. A sample of 275 respondents was selected using proportionate sampling techniques and regression analysis. The findings showed that entrepreneurial knowledge and practical skills significantly contributed to employment generation. The study recommended integrating hands-on training into entrepreneurship education. The study concluded that entrepreneurship education supports SME-driven employment creation.

Prasannath (2024) investigated the effect of entrepreneurship education on venture creation among young entrepreneurs in selected developing economies. The objective of the study was to assess the influence of cognitive, affective, and psychomotor competencies on venture creation. The population is comprised of young entrepreneurs across selected developing countries. A sample of 410 respondents was analysed using structural equation modelling. The findings revealed that all three entrepreneurial competency dimensions had significant positive effects on venture creation outcomes. The study recommended adopting a multidimensional approach to entrepreneurship education. The study concluded that holistic entrepreneurship education enhances venture creation.

METHODOLOGY

Research design adopted was correlational and cross-sectional. Purposive sample of 265 youths in Ahoada East metropolis was selected. The basic source of data collection was structured questionnaires four -Likert- scale of agreed, strongly agreed, disagreed and strongly disagreed. The research questionnaire is through mail with the help of researcher facilitators. The research adopted content validity with reliability test and retest with the same statistical tools. Statistical tool, the researcher uses Pearson's product moment coefficient correlation (PPMCC) to test the hypotheses at .05 alpha level. Decision rule: the perfect positive correlation is denoted as (R=1), perfect negative correlation is denoted as (R= -1) and zero correlation is denoted as (R=0). Also, accept Ho if alpha level is equal to 0.05 or greater than otherwise reject and accept H1 P -value is less than otherwise reject.

RESULTS

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant relationship between the cognitive domain and youth empowerment in Ahoada East Government Area Rivers State.

Table 1: Pearson correlations of relationship between cognitive domain and youths Empowerment

Variables		Cognitive	Youths Empowerment
Cognitive Domain	Pearson Correlation	1	.684**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	265	

Youths Empowerment	Pearson Correlation	.684**	1
	Sig. (2- tailed)	.000	
	N		265

Correlation is significant at the .05 level (2-tailed).

The results in Table 1 shows the Pearson product moment correlation analysis conducted to examine the relationship between the cognitive domain and youth empowerment in Ahoada East Local Government Area of Rivers State. The findings indicate a correlation coefficient of $r = .684$ with a p-value of .000 based on a sample size of $N = 265$.

This correlation coefficient reflects a strong positive relationship between the cognitive domain and youth empowerment. This means that improvements in cognitive domain factors such as knowledge, understanding, reasoning ability, and intellectual skills are associated with corresponding increases in youth empowerment outcomes. In practical terms, youths who demonstrate higher levels of cognitive development are more likely to show greater empowerment in terms of decision-making ability, problem-solving capacity, and productive engagement.

The probability value ($p = .000$) is less than the .05 level of significance, indicating that the observed relationship is statistically significant and unlikely to have occurred by chance. Therefore, the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant relationship between the cognitive domain and youth empowerment is rejected.

The analysis provided strong empirical evidence that the cognitive domain significantly and positively relates to youth empowerment in Ahoada East Local Government Area of Rivers State. This suggested that initiatives aimed at strengthening youths' cognitive skills can play an important role in enhancing empowerment outcomes. This finding is consistent with Okafor (2020), who found that entrepreneurship education significantly influenced self-employment among graduates in Anambra State.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant relationship between the affective domain and youth empowerment in Ahoada East Government Area Rivers State.

Table 2: Pearson correlations of the relationship between affective domain and youths empowerment

Variables		Affective Domain	Youths Empowerment
Affective domain	Pearson Correlation	1	.657**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	265	
Youths Empowerment	Pearson Correlation	.657**	1
	Sig. (2- tailed)	.000	
	N		265

Correlation is significant at the .05 level (2-tailed).

The results in Table 2 presented the Pearson product moment correlation analysis examining the relationship between the affective domain and youth empowerment in Ahoada East Local Government Area of Rivers State. The analysis shows a correlation coefficient of $r = .657$ with a p-value of .000 based on a sample size of $N = 265$.

The correlation coefficient of .657 indicates a strong positive relationship between the affective domain and youth empowerment. This suggested that increases in affective domain

attributes such as attitudes, values, motivation, interest, and emotional disposition are associated with higher levels of youth empowerment. In practical terms, youths who display more positive attitudes, stronger motivation, and constructive value systems tend to be more empowered and actively engaged in personal and community development.

The significance value ($p = .000$) is below the .05 level of significance, which means the relationship is statistically significant and not due to random variation. Therefore, the null hypothesis stating that there is no significant relationship between the affective domain and youth empowerment is rejected.

The findings indicated that the affective domain has a significant and positive relationship with youth empowerment in Ahoada East Local Government Area of Rivers State, highlighting the importance of emotional and attitudinal development in youth empowerment programmes. The result also aligns with Eze and Nwankwo (2021a,b), who found that entrepreneurship education positively influenced employment generation and economic empowerment in Anambra State.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant relationship between the psychomotor domain and youths' employment in Ahoada East Government Area Rivers State.

Table 3: Pearson correlations of the relationship between affective domain and youths empowerment

Variables		Psychomotor Domain	Youths Empowerment
Affective domain	Pearson Correlation	1	.657**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	265	
Youths Empowerment	Pearson Correlation	.657**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N		265

Correlation is significant at the .05 level (2-tailed).

The results in Table 3 shows the Pearson product moment correlation analysis conducted to determine the relationship between the psychomotor domain and youth empowerment in Ahoada East Local Government Area of Rivers State (although the table heading appears to contain a labeling error by repeating “affective domain”). Using a sample size of $N = 265$, the analysis produced a correlation coefficient of $r = .657$ with a p-value of .000.

The correlation coefficient of .657 indicates a strong positive relationship between the psychomotor domain and youth empowerment. This implies that higher levels of psychomotor development such as practical skills, technical abilities, vocational competence, and hands-on performance are associated with higher levels of youth empowerment. In practical terms, youths who possess stronger practical and technical skills are more likely to be empowered through improved employability, productivity, and self-reliance.

The reported significance value ($p = .000$) is less than the .05 level of significance, showing that the relationship is statistically significant and not due to chance. Therefore, the null hypothesis stating that there is no significant relationship between the psychomotor domain and youths' empowerment/employment is rejected.

The findings indicated that the psychomotor domain has a significant and positive relationship with youth empowerment in Ahoada East Local Government Area of Rivers State, underscoring the importance of skill acquisition and practical training in youth empowerment

initiatives. Uche and Bassey (2023) found that entrepreneurial competencies and practical skills contributed significantly to employment generation among SMEs.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of the study, it is concluded that entrepreneurship education plays a critical role in promoting youths' empowerment in Ahoada East Local Government Area Rivers State. The cognitive domain enhances entrepreneurial knowledge, opportunity awareness, and decision-making capacity, which supports venture creation for employment generation and job creation empowerment. The affective domain strengthens entrepreneurial attitudes, resilience, confidence, motivation, risk identification, and innovation mindset, enabling individuals to pursue and sustain business ventures. The psychomotor domain equips youths with practical skills and hands-on abilities necessary for effective business operations and job creation. Government Supportive policies simplified regulatory procedures, and access to entrepreneurship support programmes enhance the translation of entrepreneurial knowledge and skills into tangible venture outcomes. Where the political environment is favourable, entrepreneurs are better positioned to create jobs and achieve economic empowerment. Overall, the study concludes that entrepreneurship education, when supported by a conducive political environment, is a powerful tool for addressing unemployment, promoting self-employment, and improving economic wellbeing. Strengthening entrepreneurship education and policy support is therefore essential for sustainable venture creation and economic development.

Basically, this study has added to the stock of literature and empirical review on the following areas: content scope of the concept; entrepreneurship education relationship between youths' empowerment in Ahoada East Local Government Area, Rivers State. Also, the geographical location has not been covered by other scholars in the literature and empirical review that addressed this. This study has filled a gap that there are positive significant relationships between entrepreneurship education and youths' empowerment in Ahoada East Local Government Area, Rivers State.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made:

- Educational institutions and entrepreneurship training centres should strengthen the cognitive component of entrepreneurship education by emphasising start-up knowledge, opportunity identification, and basic business planning to enhance venture creation outcomes.
- Entrepreneurship education programmes should deliberately focus on developing positive entrepreneurial attitudes, confidence, motivation, and willingness to take calculated risks among participants.
- Practical and hands-on training should be fully integrated into entrepreneurship education to improve psychomotor skills and enable learners to apply entrepreneurial knowledge effectively in real business settings.
- Government at the local and state levels should formulate and implement supportive policies that encourage entrepreneurship education and facilitate youths' empowerment.

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